

SARAVATOBHADRA CHAKRA IN ASTROLOGY

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Abstract:

Sarvatobhadra Chakra is a tool used as a part of Transit of Planets. The term Sarvatobhadra means overall auspiciousness. Sarva - overall, Bhadra - auspiciousness. It is taken from the factors of Vedic astrology for 28 Nakshatras, 50 Nama Akshara's in Sanskrit, 12 Rasis, 30 Tithis for Krishna baksha and Suklabaksha, 7week days. The focus of SBC main stream is planetary analysis. It can be used for Variety of planetary analysis. It can be used for natal horoscope and Dasa analysis. The SBC used the Nakshatra to draw the minute predictions, making a microscopic study of the native chart. It is one of the most ancient methods of prediction, as it considers Abhijit Nakshatra. Abhijit Nakshatra is not in consideration under the other modern or later developed methods of Prediction. Veda means a special relationship between Graha in motion & other celestial bodies, which are fixed in the SBC of the native. Aspect by Graha play an important role in influencing human life, nations, and market fluctuations in commerce, trade, industries, and agricultural products. In Navamsa Veda every Nakshatra has 4 padas, for all the 28 Nakshatras, including Abhijit, have 112 Navamsa in SBC. Graha cause Veda of these Navamsa, by their opposite (front) direction, for example a Graha in 1st Pada of Kritika will cause Veda of 4th Pada of Sravana, including Pada's vowels, consonants and Nakshatra. This Navamsa Veda gives strong results when the Navamsa Rasi has also Veda.

Key Words: Nakshatra, Vowels, Consonant, Tithi, Nadi, Vara, Rasi, Graha, Veda, Transit, Latta.

Introduction:

अथातःसम्प्रवक्ष्यामिचक्रंत्रैलोक्यदीपकम्।

विख्यातंसर्वतोभद्रंसघःप्रत्ययकाशकम्।।

Sarvatobhadra is a conjunction of two Sanskrit words. "Sarvatah" means everywhere or entirely, and "Bhadra" means auspicious or well. The combination of this two words specific overall wellness. This Sarvatobhadra Chakra will illuminate the three worlds. This Chakra will enlighten us about the past, present and future and is therefore comparable to TRILOKYA DEEPA (a lamp for lighting up the Three Worlds). The Chakra is a multipurpose tool for Chart reading and Dasa prediction. It gives valuable information for the Natives chart for bad and good features based on the Nakshatras. The meaning of Sarvatobhadra Chakra is a tool that everything can be predicted only using this tool in Astrology. Astrologers in India had restructured high level of Jothish. They used Nadiamsa, and Sabta Nadi Chakra used in Sarvatobhadra Chakra. But unfortunately most Astrologers do not used in Nadiamsa & SBC. SBC is used in every area of life. SBC is used in Nakshatra based Prediction in Vedic astrology. Nakshatra based technique Proves to be very fruitful for ex., in Vimsottari or Kalachakra Dasa and in KP System.

Sarvatobhadra Chakra & Its Constituents:

Astrology is also used with Tantra and this is known as Yamal Tantra. There are 3 Yamal Tantras (i) Brahma (ii) Vishnu (iii) Rudra, these are most commonly used. SBC is part of Brahma Yamal Tantra,

Preparation of Sarvatobhadra Chakra:

ऊर्ध्वगादशविन्यस्यतिर्यगेखाम्तधादश।

एकाशीतिपदं चक्रं जायते नात्र संशयः।।

अकारादिस्वराःकोष्ठेष्वीशादिविदिशिक्रमात्।

सृष्टिमार्गवदातव्यःषोडशैवंचतुर्भमम्।।

क्रत्तिकादीनीधिष्णयानीपूर्वाशादिलिखेत्क्रमात्।

सप्तसप्तक्रमादेतान्यष्टाविंशतिःसंख्यया।।

SBC is constructed of 81 boxes. 10 lines vertical and 10 lines horizontal will make a chakra of $9 \times 9 = 81$ fields. The Chakra depends on 27 Nakshatras, the number 27 has the divisors 3 and 9 trigonal. Abijit plays a key role and gives rise to a rectangular Nakshatra chart, composed of $4 \times 7 = 28$ basic fields. Mark the four directions (east, west, north & south) and 4 sub directions (North east, south east, North west, & South west) in the chakra. Start writing from the north east direction to fill 16 boxes falling in the sub direction. SBC is good tools for chart reading and Dasa prediction. It gives valuable information about the birth chart and its Nakshatra based positive and negative features. It gives a key for Gochara (transit) predictions and can that be used as valuable addition for timing events.

Abhijit Nakshatra (Use of Special Nakshatras):

Abhijit is a span of 4°13' 20" seconds in the sign of Capricorn starting from 6°40' Makara to 10° 53' 20" Makara. This is based on the authority of Varaha Mihira. This Nakshatra is used in Ashtottari Maha Dasaa system. Aswini to Purva Ashada (20) and Dhanishta to Revathi (5). These 25 Nakshatra occupied equal distance of 13° 20' each and remaining 3 Nakshatras Uttara Ashada, Abhijit and Sravana occupying varying distance but totalling 26° 40'. For location of all Nakshatras. It is not a Nakshatra per second, but rather a division within the Capricorn sign that spans from the last quarter of Uttara Ashadha to beginning of Shravana. It is sometimes considered equivalent to Nakshatra because of the qualities of Abhijit as it affects a muhurta. The Nakshatra by virtue of their definition and their utility are 27 only. Abhijit is considered only in cases of muhurta and Mundane Astrology. Of course, people use it in astrology at time to predict that someone was born in a very auspicious time and thus to make them feel happy, but Abhijit is not a part of natal astrology. In muhurta, Abhijit is considered to be a very auspicious Nakshatra with the capability of cancelling most malefic influences present at the time. SBC uses a zodiac of 28 Nakshatras. This is a significant difference to other Nakshatra based chakras. Most of the classical chakra depend on a zodiac of 27 Nakshatras, so they are trigonal because the number 27 has only the divisors 3 and 9. So the presence of Abhijit plays a key role and gives rise to a rectangular Nakshatra chart composed of 4*7 = 28.

Method for Construct Sarvatobhadra Chakra:

अवकहडादिषुप्रच्यामटरपरताश्चदक्षिणे।

नयभजखाश्चवारुण्यंगसदचलास्तथोत्तरे।

त्रयस्त्रयोवृषाघश्वपूर्वाशादिक्रमाब्दुधैः।

राशयोद्वादशैवंतूमेषान्ताःसृष्टिःमार्गः॥

Sarvatobhadra Chakra is drawn in a rectangle of 9*9 = 81 fields. The Nakshatra belong to upper and lower row, respectively the left and right column. The corners and the 7*7 sections in the centre of the chakra are not occupied so far. The counting is clock wise. We have total 28 Nakshatra including the Abijit Nakshatra starting to Kritika in the east direction. We will have 7 Nakshatra in each direction. Kritika to Asilisha in the east. Maha to visaka in the south. Anuradha to Sravana (including Abijit) in the west. Dhanista to Bahrani in the North. Aswini is the 7th Nakshatra in the upper row. The other Nakshatras including Abhijit follow in regular manner. There are 4 corners in SBC. They have special significance. It is written that the Nakshatra Padas in neighbourhood to the corners are critical points and must be regarded in a special manner. The following Table gives the zodiac positions of the corners and their corresponding neighbourhood Padas. Abhijit is the 28th star and is located between Uttarahadha and Sravana. The last quarter of Uttarahadha and the first part of Sravana are regarded as belonging to Abhijit.

Zodiac Position:

Corner	Between Nakshatras	Corner Position	Pada before	Pada after
Right Upper	Bharani Krittika	26:40 Ar	23:20 - 26:40 Ari	26:40 Ari - 0:00-Tau
Right Lower	Aslesha- Makha	0:00 Leo	26:40 Can- 0:00 Leo	0:00- 2:20Leo
Left Lower	Vishakha- Anuradha	3:20 Sco	0:00- 3:20 Sco	3:20 6:40 Sco
Left Upper	Sravana Dhanishta	23:20 Cap	20:00- 23:20 Cap	23:20- 26:40 Cap

Sarvatobhadra Chakra:

East Direction

A	Kritika	Rohini	Mrigashira	Ardra	Punarvasu	Pushya	Ashiesha	AA
Bharani	o	A	Va/Ba	Ka	Ha	Da	oo	Magha Poorva
Ashwini	La	Lri	Taurus	Gemini	Cancer	Lree	Ma	Phalguni
Revathi	Cha	Aries	o	Sun, Tue 01-06-2011 Nanda	Ou	Leo	Ta	Uttara Phalguni
Uttra Bhadra pada	Dha	Pisces	Fri 04-09-2014 Rikta	Sat 5,10,15,30 Poorna	Mon, Wed 02-07-2012 Bhadra	Virgo	Pa/ShaN/a	Hasta
Poorva Bhadra pada	Sa	Aquarius	Aha	Thu 03-08-2013 Jaya	Am	Libra	Ra	Chitra
Shata bhisha	Ga	Aei	Capricorn	Sagittarius	Scorpio	Ae	Ta	Swati
Dhani shtha	Ree	Kha	Ja	Bh	Ya	Na	Re	Vishakha

EE	Shravana	Abhijit	U.Ashadha	P.Ashadha	Moola	Jyeshtha	Anuradha	E
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West Direction

Making prediction based on Sarvatobhadra Chakra:

- SBC is an extremely advanced course of astrology. It is an essential chakra or chart to make predictions about the native.
- The study of the Sarvatobhadra Chakra along with natal chart can help make predictions related to finance, share market, business, name of business, name of the children, and even predict the initial of the native's spouse name.
- In a broad view, it can make predictions not only on the individual but also on national levels.
- One can make an accurate prediction about the war, Political issues, result of the election, agricultural productivity, success of the business, and many more.
- It is also applicable to determine the timings of rain and its quantum.

Sarvatobhadra Chakra in Transit:

SBC is a very important tool to understand transits. When we see transit we see normal influence, but in this chakra, we can even see the influence of planets on each other even when they are not on 1 to 7 axes. This chart helps determine the predictions by studying the effect of the transit planet based on six primary personal identifiers. In SBC the Veda shows the influence of transiting (or natal) planets on various Stars, signs, tithes, Akshara's and day of the week on which native took birth based on lunar phase. These personal identifiers are the reason to make each individual a unique one. Combining all this information with the planetary transit indicates the beneficial and challenging period in the native's life.

Veda in SBC:(Concept of Veda):

ऊर्ध्वदिष्टचर्माँकीकेकसौबुधार्गवौ।
 समदिष्टचर्जीवेन्दूशनिराहुअधोशो।।
 नीचस्थोध्वदिष्टश्वउच्चैरधोनिरिसयेत्।
 समश्वपार्श्वतोदिष्टस्त्रिधादिष्टःप्रकथ्यते।।

Each Stars has 3 Vedas (Veda means influence) – Right, left & forward.

Veda means transfer of energy. The Veda of benefice considered to be favourable and that of malefic are considered as unfavourable. The influence is stronger if they are considered as unfavourable. The influence is stronger if they are exalted and retrograde while weaker if they are debilitated.

Types of Vedas:

- Across Veda (Opposite) – When seen from a transiting planet, the bodies falling across in the SBC comes under Veda from the said planet. When the planets transit on the Stars in the left wall of the chakra, the across Veda will be on the Stars towards the right and vice versa, similarly when the planet transit the Stars on the upper wall of the chart, the across Veda will be downward. This Veda is more effective if the planets are in normal motion or stationary.
- Backward – like forward Veda, but in negative (anti clock wise) direction.
- Forward – this Veda appears if we travel SBC in diagonal manner until we reach the next Star at the border of the chakra. Forward motion means that we have to go in positive. Clockwise (Zodiacal) direction.

Examples:

- Ashwini has forward Veda to Rohini, opposite Veda to Purvaphalguni and backward Veda to Jyeshtha.
- Swati has forward Veda to Jyeshtha, opposite Veda to Sathabish and backward Veda to Rohini.
- Purvashadha has forward Veda to Uttara Bhadra, opposite Veda to Ardra and backward Veda to Hasta.
- Kritika has forward Veda to Vaisakha, opposite Veda to Shravana and backward Veda to Bharani.

Vedas of Individual Points in the Zodiac (Veda illustration):

शन्यकेराहुकेत्वाशःक्रशःशेषाशूभग्रहाः।
 क्रमूक्तोबुधःक्रूरःक्षीणचन्द्रस्तथैवच।।
 यस्मिन्क्षेस्थितःखेटस्तत्तेवेधत्रयंभवेत्।
 ग्रहदिवशेनात्रवामसम्मुखदक्षिणे।।

Veda of Nakshatra is the only one way of interpretation. The argument of Vedas can also be applied to individual points of the Zodiac. Each individual point of the Zodiac has three Vedas. The Veda point is reached if we make a proportional consideration (rule of three) regarding the longitude of a planet. For example, the second degree of Ashwini has its opposite point in the second degree of Purvaphalguni (counted from the end): 24 Leo. Regions of the Zodiac can be calculated in a simple manner, i.e., by taking the start and end point of the region.

Examples:

- The exaltation points of the Sun (10:00 Aries) has opposite Veda with 16:40 Leo.
- The debilitation points of the sun (10:00 Libra) has opposite Veda with 16:40 Aquarius.
- The mooltrikona of the sun (0-20 Leo) has opposite Veda with 6:40 – 26:40 Aries
- The exaltation point of Jupiter (3 Cancer) has opposite Veda with 0 Sagittarius.
- The debilitation point of Jupiter (3 Capricorn) has opposite Veda with 30 Taurus, etc.

Nakshatra	Right Veda	Left Veda	Direct Veda
Ashwini	Jyeshtha	Rohini	Purvaphalguni
Bharani	Anuradha	Kritika	Magha
Kritika	Bharani	Vaisakha	Shravana
Rohini	Ashwini	Swati	Abhijit
Mrigasira	Revathi	Chitra	U.Aashaadha
Ardra	U.Bhadra	Hasta	P. Aashaadha
PunaVasu	P.Bhadra	U.Phalguna	Moola
Pushya	Shatabhishak	P. Phalguna	Jyeshtha
Ashlesha	Dhanishta	Magha	Anuradha

Upagrahas in Veda:

भुक्तंभोग्यं तथाक्षान्तं क्रूरगहेण च ।
शुभशुभेषु कार्येषु वर्जनीयं प्रयन्ततः ॥
वक्रगेदक्षिणादिष्टवम्दिष्टिश्च शीघ्रगे ।
मध्यचारे तथा मध्याजेयाभौमादिपंचके ॥

The Nakshatra occupied Sun in a particular day, these nakshatras indicate malefic day for all purpose and failures if some activity is carried out on that day. The nakshatras are afflicted along with Janmanakshatra by malefic conjunction or aspect, the malefic result will be more serious. Two malefic grahas are jointly afflicting above sensitive nakshatras 5,8,14,18,21,22,23,24 are 100% malefic days and should be avoided for all purposes. Otherwise, malefic events may take place. The Janma Nakshatra is occupied by Upagraha, this indicates a serious warning. It may cause bad health, accident, dispute. If a malefic graha and Upagraha falls on Janmanakshatra, this is a serious indication and may cause death.

Nakshatra of Upagraha from Sun's Nakshatra	Results
Sun's own Nakshatra	Malefic results
5 th Nakshatra - Vidyutmuk	Death of child and fall
8 th Nakshatra - Shoola	Death of husband and bleeding
14 th Nakshatra - Sannipata	Death of husband, Sun and fever
18 th Nakshatra - Ke	Death of brother in law
21 th Nakshatra - Ulka	Financial loss and danger
22 nd Nakshatra - Kampa	Death of relatives and cold.
23 rd Nakshatra - Bajra	Setbacks in profession and danger
24 th Nakshatra - Nirghata	Setbacks in profession and danger

Effect of Planets:

The planets influence of benefic enhance good fortune, influence of malefic cause suffering and destruction. The connect of the benefic are Jupiter, Venus, well associated Mercury and strong Moon. The malefic are Saturn, Rahu, Mars and Ketu and the Sun. Association of Mercury with Saturn and Rahu makes it extremely diabolical while association of Sun and Mars makes it only mildly malefic. Similarly dark moon Krishna Chaturdashi to Shukla Pratipada is quite malefic while from Shukla Dwitiya to Shukla Ashtami and Krishna Thrayodashi are mildly malefic.

Planets	The specific effects
Sun	Misunderstanding & ego related problems
Moon	Pleasant happenings if strong and Vice-Versa
Mars	Loss of wealth
Mercury	Learning and efficiency at work
Jupiter	Overall prosperity and wellbeing
Venus	Sexual enjoyment and entertainment
Saturn	Sickness
Raghu	Deception and Cheating
Ketu	Accidents and sudden happenings

Strength of Influence:

Based on the dignity of the planets causing Veda, the influence will be modified the following way:

Exaltation - 3 times
 Retrogression - 2 times
 Debilitation - ½ time
 Other dignity -1 time (normal)

If a malefic Planets gets exalted or retrograde, becomes extremely malefic. It is desirable to have benefics are retrograde or exalted and malefic as debilitated.

Effects of Veda on Different elements: (PANCHANGA DETAILS)

Although we have discussed on the Veda of planets on the vital Nakshatras, it is important to note the Veda on various other elements of the Sarvatobhadra chakra that is the Akshara (alphabet),Tithi (Lunar Day), Vara (Week days), Rasi (Sign), andNakshatras (Stars). Each element governs over various area of life as used in the judgement of Panchangam. In addition to the Janma and other vital nakshatra, native’s Janmatithi, vara,rasi, and Akshara can also be noted. Benefic and malefic Veda on these elements will have good or bad impacts on different areas of life as mentioned below:

Vara(Weekday):

The week day lord governs over the life force of the native. A strong week day lord gives good health and faster recovery from disease and health disorders. While weak weekday lord fails to do so. Applying this principle in Sarvatobhadra chakra, we can say that malefic Veda on the Janmavara (the day on which the person is born) can have negative impact on the native’s health and vice-versa.

Akshara (Alphabet):

Like Moon, the Akshara is also related to survival of the native in the world. While moon sustains by giving comfort and good living condition, the name sustains by giving a favourable image. If there are malefic Vedas to the 1st Akshara of the name, the native’s image may suffer and vice-versa.

Akshara:

- A, V, K, H, Da in the east,
- M, T, P, R, T in the south
- N, Y, Bh, J, Kh in the West
- G, S, D, Ch, L in the North.

Tithi(Lunar Day):

शेषेषुकोष्ठकेष्वेवंनन्दादितिपंचक्रम्।
 वराणांसप्तकलेख्यंभौमाघचक्रमेणवै॥
 भौमादित्यैचनन्दायांभद्रामांबुधशीतम्।
 जपतोचगुरुःप्रोस्तोरिक्तयांभार्गवस्तथा॥
 पूणायांशनिवारश्चलेख्योचक्रेत्रनिश्चितम्।
 इत्येषसर्वतोभद्रविस्तारःकीर्तितोमया॥

In the Panchanga scheme, Tithi rules over prosperity and has a strong say on the finances in addition to the overall comfort and wellbeing. Using the same principle here, if there are malefic Veda on the native’s Janmatithi, the native will face financial troubles as well as general lack of comfort. Malefic Veda on the Purnatithi in the muhurta chart of an ailing person can show death. The tithi’s are grouped in to five groups.

Tithi Lunar days		Week days & results
Nanda	Pratipad, Shasthi, Ekadasi (1,6,11) Tithi	Sunday & Tuesday in the East
Bhadra	Tvitiya, Saptami, Dvadasi (2,7,12)	Wed & Mon in the south
Jaya	Tritiya, Astami, Trayodasi (3,8,13)	Thursday in the west
Rikta	Chaturthi, Navami, Chaturdasi (4,9,14)	Friday in the North
Purna	Panchami, Dasami, Purnima, Amavasya (5,10,15)	Saturday in the centre
Nanda		Joy
Bhadra		Auspicious
Jaya		Victory
Rikta		Empty
Purna		Complete

Rasi (Zodiac Signs):

The Rasi governs over all the resources which we get from the mothernature. The Veda on the Rasi would show accessibility to various resources. In addition, the Janmarasi has a strong bearing on the health of the native while the Janma Lagna has a strong bearing on his intellectual faculty. The malefic Veda on the Janmarasi can cause health troubles while that on the Janma Lagna can show incorrect application of intelligence and incorrect decision making.

This can also be used in conjunction to the natal chart. In the natal chart each sign will be associated with a particular house. Malefic Veda on a sign can trouble the associated house. If there are inauspicious yoga’s

in a particular house, malefic Veda on that sign can aggravate it further, while benefic Veda can alleviate the trouble to certain extent. A favourable yoga can be stunted during a particular period if there are malefic Veda on the associated sign and the yoga can flourish under benefic Veda.

Taurus, Gemini, Cancer	-	East
Leo, Virgo, Libra	-	South
Scorpio, Sagittarius, Capricorn	-	West
Aquarius, Pisces, Aries	-	North

Dasa & Antardasa:

The dasa and antardasa of the planets involved in inauspicious yoga in the horoscope can cause tremendous suffering, if both of them simultaneously cause Veda to a vital nakshatra in the area related to the nakshatra. One has to judge the result based on functional and natural nature of the planets involved as well as the yoga they form in the natal chart. The adverse yoga's give the adverse results during unfavourable transits and hence one has to watch out the transiting dasaantardasa lord not only with respect to normal transits but also from the view point of Sarvatobhadra chakra.

Dasa & antardasa of benefic planets can give their benefic results when they have benefic Veda on some vital nakshatra. Based on the functional nature of the planets and the yoga they form one among the mentioned vital nakshatra would become more important and a wise astrologer should ascertain that vital nakshatra before pronouncing the results. For example, for the matter of yoga related to power, status and fame, abhisheka nakshatra becomes extremely important. If the planets contributing to the yoga simultaneously have Veda on the abhisheka nakshatra during their periods and sub periods, it can be predicted that the yoga will yield good result.

Special Nakshatras: (Nadi Nakshatras)

Nadi means pulse and these Nakshatras offer secret clues to chart analysis. Nadiare pulse which flow in our body and connect the various energy points. How these pulses are flowing the birth chart is analysed through the Nadinakshatra to show where the blocks are and where the information is flowing smoothly. Navatara form the basis of Nadinakshatras and it is used in Muhurta where it helps in planning an event in relation to the moon's transit. The principle is expanded further for chart analysis. Other points of view like lagna, sun and dashalord, must also be taken into account.

Navatara and Nadi Nakshatra:

Nakshatra type		1 st paryay		2 nd Paryay		3 rd Paryay
Janma-birth	1		10	Karma	19	Aadhana
Sampat-wealth	2		11		20	
Vipat-danger	3		12		21	
Kshema-happiness	4	Jati	13		22	
Prayatak-obstacles	5		14		23	Vinasha
Sadhana-attainment	6		15		24	
Naidhana-poverty	7		16	Sanghatika	25	Manasa
Mitra-friend	8	Matru	17		26	
Param Mitra-great friend	9		18	Samudaya	27	Abhishekha

Nadi Nakshatra Rules:

There are many ways to use Nadinakshatras. Navatara and Nadinakshatras table is made and analysed for static and dynamic chart analysis. It is also used for compatibility. Static analysis how the planets relate to each other via Nadinakshatra in the natal chart. This will give clues as to how the Nadinakshatras affect the chart. Dasha, bhuktis, and its karakas. Karakas placed in negative nakshatras can be damaged. Analyse from the Moon, Sun and lagna points of view, and study what energy each nakshatra is reflecting.

Transit analysis extremely useful as the planets move through the nakshatra mandala, they will connect to the different Nadis and create situations that may not be understood through normal analysis. In Compatibility analysis Nadinakshatras are important. Certain nakshatras from the natal Moon nakshatras are extremely negative. Choosing partners with those nakshatras can bring unhappiness and sorrow.

Veda of Stars from Birth Star by Planets and their Vedha Results:

1 st Janma Nakshatra	Janma	Danger to native and death - if Veda by 2 strong malefic planets
2 nd Nakshatra	Sampat	Wealth & prosperity -benefic aspect necessary
3 rd Nakshatra	Vipat	Accident if aspected by 2 strong malefic planets
4 th Nakshatra	Kshema	Happiness & prosperity if aspected by benefic planet
5 th Nakshatra	Prayatak	Loss of business & obstacles depending on malefic aspect
6 th Nakshatra	Sadhaka	Success in efforts, depending on sincere efforts
7 th Nakshatra	Naidhana	Sudden death & loss if Veda by 2 strong malefic planets
8 th Nakshatra	Mitra	Financial gain & Success through friend

9 th Nakshatra	Param Mitra	Financial gain & Success through very intimate friend
10 th Nakshatra	Karma	Disputes, sufferings and unhappiness
11 th Nakshatra	Sampat	Wealth & prosperity
12 th Nakshatra	Vipat	Sickness & accident
13 th Nakshatra	Kshema	Happiness & prosperity
14 th Nakshatra	Pratwara	Loss of business & obstruction
15 th Nakshatra	Sadhaka	Success in efforts depends on sincere effort
16 th Nakshatra	Sanghatika	Financial loss & disappointment
17 th Nakshatra	Mitra	Financial success & gain through friend
18 th Nakshatra	Samudayik	Sudden setbacks, malefic results and harm
19 th Nakshatra	Adhan	Separation & foreign travel
20 th Nakshatra	Sampath	Wealth & prosperity
21 st Nakshatra	Vipath	Sickness & accident
22 nd Nakshatra	Kshemya	Happiness & prosperity
23 rd Nakshatra	Vinasha	Dispute, sudden death and misunderstanding
24 th Nakshatra	Sadhana	Success in efforts
25 th Nakshatra	Manas	Destruction of family and community
26 th Nakshatra	Desha	Defeat by enemy
27 th Nakshatra	Abhisheka	Power and achievement, Positive and supportive

Sarvatobhadra Chakra in Muhurta:

Naturally all our daily activities based on Muhurtas are for common purpose. Astrology has prescribed special muhurtas for each auspicious activity like entering a new house, marriage, buying vehicle and other things, postnatal ceremonies, education, new business travels etc., In a SBC when some benefic grahas in motion transit Janmanakshatra and other consonants of native, create most auspicious Muhurtas for all types of activities. This Muhurta should however be synchronized with auspicious muhurta according to natal chakra of native.

Benefic and malefic nakshatras should be clearly marked in SBC. Whenever Sun transit any direction in SBC, East, South, West or North, Rasi, Nakshatra, Navamsa etc. become combust & most inauspicious. Whenever any malefic Graha is causing Veda of a particular pada of a particular Nakshatra, whole Nakshatra become malefic & should be avoided. The day which is owned by Janma Nakshatra and is occupied by all malefic Grahas, and the day on which Nakshatras 10, 19, 12, 16, 23, 25 are occupied by Sun, Mars, Saturn or malefic Moon should be avoided.

SBC determines the auspicious muhurtas to enhance the certainty of success and pleasure. SBC is best method to fix a Muhurta (Election Astrology). Usually when we do Muhurta we ignore the tithis. These are certain tithis which are not favourable for a native and when we fix a muhurta, we go by general rules. There will be certain lagnas, certain days of week or certain tithis which are not good for the native like marriage or starting a new venture.

Graha Latta and Nakshatra Aspects:

Position of Latta Nakshatra from a Nakshatra occupied by a Graha	Behind/front for counting	Result	Results if Latta falls on Janma Nakshatra
12 th from Sun's Nakshatra (sun's Latta)	Front	Death, defeat	Professional setbacks and loss
3 rd from Mar's Nakshatra (Mar's Latta)	Front	Set backs	Setbacks, danger, death and loss
6 th from Guru's Nakshatra (Guru's Latta)	Front	Illness	Loss of relatives, separation and sufferings
8 th from Saturn's Nakshatra (Saturn's Latta)	Front	Danger, fear	Death, serious danger, loss, theft and sickness
22 nd from Moon's Nakshatra (Moon's Latta)	Behind	Danger, death	Setbacks, danger, travel and disease
7 th from Buda's Nakshatra (Buda's Latta)	Behind	Death of relative	Separation, loss and confusion
5 th from Sukran's Nakshatra (sukaran's Latta)	Behind	Setbacks	Loss of relatives, discord with wife and sex disease
9 th from Ra & Ke Nakshatra (Ra & Ke Latta)	Behind	Death	Financial loss and danger

Some malefic sensitive points are determined with help Latta Chakra. Latta means kick by a Graha, a malefic influence on a particular Nakshatra at a particular distance by a particular Graha. In determining the auspicious time, avoid the above Nakshatras.

Counting should be done from the Nakshatra occupied by each Graha either forward or backward as indicated in the above chart. Ragu being always retrograde, backward of Ragu means forward of Ragu's face. Front indicates clockwise direction, behind means anticlockwise direction. Latta Nakshatra indicates only the malefic Nakshatra of the day whether the Latta is by a benefic Graha or a malefic Graha. In Prasana find out the Nakshatra of the day & then find out the Nakshatra occupied by other Grahas. If day's Nakshatra is influenced by any Latta Nakshatra, the results will be according to that Graha's Latta. In Muhurta, suppose native's planning to enter in a new house on a day which is occupied by Revati. This Nakshatra is not Latta Nakshatra from Sun, Mars, Guru, Saturn as they do not occupy 12th, 3rd, 6th, 8th Nakshatra in forward position. Similarly, Chandran, Budan, Sukran, Ragu / Ketu do not occupy 22nd, 7th, 5th, 9th Nakshatra in backward position. This means the day is benefic and Latta does not exist on that day. Sun occupies Kritika Nakshatra, the 12th Nakshatra from Kritika is Chitra Nakshatra, which is having Latta of Sun. When the day's Nakshatra the native's having Latta of any Graha, it should be avoided for any auspicious work.

Transit Chart:

A Transit chart is nothing but a progressed natal chart, Sarvatobhadra chakra can be verily used, to predict the lucky nakshatra, tithi, vowel, graharashi and avoid Veda ones. One can correlate a horoscope's nakshatra, tithi and fixed dashas with transits, with the below algorithm.

The chart of Tithi, Bootha and Graha:

Tithi	Bootha	Graha
Nanda	Agni	Kuja
Bhadra	Prithivi	Budha
Jaya	Akash	Guru
Rikta	Jala	Shukra
Poorna	Vayu	Shani

Kumaraswamiyam: (Sloka for Vedha of stars)

Kumaraswami means Lord Muruga, Son of Lord Shiva. Initially Lord Shiva is narrating the importance of astrology to Lord Muruga. He in return passes it on to Rishi Agasthiyar that our current deeds are based on past Karmas.

இயமுறந்தார்வேம்முடியாமினன்றினநோக்கயன்றார்
 இறைசோதிமகமதிநாட்கெரிசுடர்கண்டார்சேய்
 கயநடவிவிதுப்புதனேரசிதனளவுளநாள்
 கவுண்டபமவுணுகநோய்முகன்குருநாட்கதிக
 முயலகனேர்தாரளவான்முதற்கலையும்பனைநேர்
 மூன்றறியும்பரணிசுடர்முறமுமியமுடித்தீ
 பயம்வலமற்றதுகவுணாற்கோணமற்றானைமாய்ப்
 பவுமனெனமனுறல்பரிநேர்பகர்வதிதற்காமே

Chart Analysis:

Date of Birth: 07 January 1991
 Time of Birth: 04-04-00 Pm
 Place of Birth:Coimbatore

		As Mars	
	Rasi		Ke (JU)
Venus Ragu Saturn			
Sun Me			MO

		As Mars	
	D-1 (Moon)		Ke (JU)
Venus Ragu			
Saturn Sun	Me		MO

Navatara and Nadi Nakshatras from the moon							
Nakshatra type	Pl		1 st Paryay		2 nd Paryay		3 rd Paryay
Janma-birth	Mo	1	Hasta-Moon Janma	10	Shravana-Vens Karma	19	Rohini Aadhana
Sampat-Wealth	Ma	2	Chitra	11	Dhanishta	20	Mrigasira Lagna
Vipat-danger	Ra	3	Swati	12	Shatabhishak	21	Ardra
Kahema-happiness	Ju	4	Vishakha - Jati	13	PurvaBhadra	22	Punarvasu
Prayatak-obstacles	Sa	5	Anuradha	14	UttaraBhadra	23	Pushya-Ketu Vinasha
Sadhana-attainment	Me	6	Jyeshtha	15	Revati	24	Ashlesha-Jupiter
Naidhana-poverty	Ke	7	Mula Mercury	16	Ashwin Sanghatika	25	Magha Manasa
Mitra-friend	Ve	8	PurvaAshadha- Sun Matru	17	Bharani	26	PurvaPhalguni Desha
ParamMitra-great friend	Su	9	UttraAshadha- Saturn Ragu	18	Krittika-Mars Samudaya	27	UttaraPhalguni Abhishekha

On the Day of Natives father death: - (i.e., on 29th June 2005)

- On that particular day The Malefic planet Sun is placed in Vipat (Danger) Nadi Nakshatra. Another Malefic planets Saturn, Mercury, and Venus is placed in Pratyak (Obstacles) Nadi Nakshatra.
- Natal Chart Sun and Mercury is placed in 8th house of Sagittarius. Saturn, Ragu and Venus are placed in 9th house of Capricorn.

Vimsottari Dasa:

- Ragu MD 29/03/2001 – 30/03/2019
- Jupiter AD 10/12/2003 – 05/05/2006
- Venus PD 13/02/2005 – 09/07/2005
- He was running Ragu dasa, who is also badhaka for Moon (Hasta) Nakshatra.
- Sun is Pitru Karaka, Sun is posited in Ragu (Ardra) Star, 14th Star (sannipata) of Upagraha from Sun's star, it gives death.
- Sun has Vedha (Aspect) on Saturn (Uttara Bhadra) and Janma Star (Hasta) it is 21st star (Ulka) of Upagraha from Sun's Star, it gives danger.
- Moon, Ragu and Mars posited in Mercury (Revati) star and vedha on Mars (Mrigasira), Sun (P Phalguni), and Ketu (Moola).

On the Day of Natives Spouse Ectopic Pregnancy (operated): - (i.e., on 06th June 2019)

- On that particular day Moon is placed in Prayatak (obstacles) in Nava Tara & Saturn (Pushya) star placed in Prayatak (obstacles) in Nava Tara and 23rd star of Vinasha in NadiNakshatra.
- Jupiter is Karaka of children. It is posited in 23rd star of Janmanakshatra, this is Latta (Kick) star. If a planet is transitting in a Latta star will gives a malefic impact on a Natives life.
- Mercury is placed in Vipat (danger) in Nava Tara.
- Ragu Placed in (Shatabhishak) 5th star of upagraha for sun's star, it will give the result of child death.
- Venus is placed in Sun (Krittika) 23rd star of upagraha for sun's star it is a karaka for operation, Separation and death. Venus Vedha on Jupiter (Vishakha) star. This is 24th upagraha of sun, it will give the result of obstacles in family.

Vimsottari Dasa:

- Jupiter MD 30/03/2019 – 30/03/2035
- Jupiter AD 30/03/2019 – 17/05/2021
- Jupiter PD 30/03/2019 – 12/07/2019
- Lagna posited in Ketu (Moola) Star, Vedha on Mars, Ragu & Jupiter (Punarvasu).
- Jupiter posited in Mercury (Jyeshtha) Star. Vedha (Aspect) on Moon, and Saturn (Pushya) star, Ketu (Ashwini)star, and Ragu (swati) Star.
- Moon posited in Saturn (pushya) star. Vedha on Jupiter®.
- Mars & Ragu posited in Jupiter (Punarvasu) star. Vedha on LagnaKetu(moola) star. Jupiter (P.Phalguni) and Sun (U.Phalguni).
- All these tantamount had been given a malefic impact on his life.

Conclusion:

SBC is best method to fix a Muhurta (Election Astrology) – Usually when we do Muhurta we ignore the tithis. These are certain tithis which are not favourable for a native and when we fix a muhurta, we go by general rules. There will be certain lagnas, certain days of week or certain tithis which are not good for the native like marriage or starting a new venture. Sarvatobhadra Chakra is a very efficient tool used for natal as well as mundane Astrology predictions. This chart analyses the prediction of overall wellness.SBC gives rare insights into a horoscope which is not possible from a Rasi chart alone, it has to be used along with D1 chart. Use of Sarvatobhadra Chakra in the naming of business/children etc., Sarvatobhadra Chakra in Share Market Use of Sarvatobhadra Chakra in Prashna Astrology. Use of Sarvatobhadra Chakra in Muhurt.

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